

NAVIGATING LEADERSHIP: AN IN-DEPTH EXPLORATION ON THE CHALLENGES AND EXPERIENCES OF ELEMENTARY STUDENT LEADERS IN ASUNCION DISTRICT

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Navigating Leadership: An In-Depth Exploration on the Challenges and Experiences of Elementary Student Leaders in Asuncion District

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Abstract

The main objective of this qualitative study was to gain a comprehensive understanding of the experiences of elementary student leaders: president, vice president and secretary. Using purposive sampling and inclusion criteria, the participating fourteen elementary student leaders from five elementary schools in Asuncion District were identified. Seven (7) of them participated in the in-depth interview and another seven (7) participated in the focus group discussion. Results revealed the experiences of the participants: considering the essential traits and duties of student-leaders, humility in leadership, difficulty in balancing leadership responsibility and academics and embracing the responsibilities wholeheartedly. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deemed the following coping strategies essential: establishing collaboration with others, creating a support system and lastly keeping oneself motivated. Upon reflecting on their entire experience, they arrived at the following insights: must possess various leadership abilities, leadership empowers communication and confidence and lastly effective time management and prioritization in leadership. Although it might be difficult for elementary student leaders in the Asuncion district to juggle their leadership responsibilities with social and academic obligations, these experiences are crucial for their development as leaders and as people. Schools should encourage these young leaders by offering mentorship programs and formal training that enable them to successfully handle these obstacles. The results of this study were deemed significant by the participants, teachers, parents, students and researchers.

Keywords: *experiences, elementary student leaders, thematic analysis, qualitative research, Philippines*

Introduction

The Supreme Pupil Government (SPG) is a collaborative initiative between learners and schools aimed at enhancing educational services. It acts as a foundation for elementary students to cultivate leadership skills and social competencies. The SPG provides opportunities for students to grow as effective leaders and responsible members of society, promoting the values of participatory democracy. As a school-based organization, its primary goal aims to equip pupils to become outstanding citizens in the near future while fostering their skills and potential. Through teamwork, it strives to achieve academic excellence and ensure quality education (Gregorio, 2019).

In Turkey, young students often have limited exposure to leadership roles and opportunities, operating in environments that are more equalitarian than hierarchical. In student organizations, there are typically minimal external motivators, whether rewards or penalties, and the duration of both membership and leadership roles is usually short and small in scope. To address this, the Practices of Leadership was introduced to enhance the leadership abilities of young students (Kouzes & Posner, 2018).

In Philippines, student leaders often experience a decline in academic performance due to the strain of demanding situations that lead to academic burnout. Burnout arises from emotional exhaustion and the challenge of dealing with uncooperative peers while striving to excel academically. Research on the leadership performance of schoolchildren has examined the interplay of various personal factors, such as the connection between cognition and motivation. Additionally, contextual factors, like a student's readiness to take on social responsibilities, significantly impact both academic and social outcomes. Students who embrace greater responsibility tend to develop a more positive approach to their studies, ultimately achieving higher academic success (Alambra & Aggabao, 2020).

The study needs urgent research attention through examining early leadership encounters, researchers can get important knowledge on how these early experiences mold people into accountable and involved members of society. This information can help design leadership initiatives and regulations that support individual development and strengthen society. On the other hand, this study holds significant social relevance as it delves into the early years of leadership development because elementary student leaders play a vital role in shaping responsible and engaged citizens who contribute positively to society.

The researcher have come across relevant studies such as, the study of Patrick (2022) "Student Leadership and Student Government" and that of Lucero (2021) "Students' Satisfaction on the Supreme Student Government Services: Basis for Action Plan" and that of Arribado (2016) "Efficacy of Supreme Student Government in Three Secondary Schools" which they focused on satisfaction of students having standing role within education leadership structure of secondary and tertiary student leaders. This study stands out due to its unique focus on exploring the experiences and challenges faced by elementary student leaders, particularly delving into their time management strategies. This field of study is particularly marginalized in the body of current knowledge and provides insight into a crucial aspect of early leadership development. These premises prompted the researcher to propose this study.

Copies of the study will be shared at various research conferences and with related organizations to facilitate knowledge exchange and

utilization of the practical use of discoveries. Therefore, the importance and result of this study will reach a wider audience, helping to address the problems discussed and implement the suggested recommendations.

The purpose of this phenomenological study was to gain insight and coping mechanism from the lived experiences of the Elementary Student Leaders: president, vice president and secretary in Asuncion District. Hence, this study highlighted the insight and difficulties of the elementary student leaders, coping mechanism and realization along their leadership journey. Henceforth, this targeted the explication of the factors that underscore the process of elementary student leaders.

At this stage in the research, the extracurricular activities encountered by the elementary student leaders will be emphasize as they work towards their academic and leadership goals. Also, valuing the stress and challenges they encounter in their leadership journey. This study aims to dig deep into understanding how this challenges affects them and their pursuit of academic and leadership success.

Research Questions

This research aimed to delve on the lived experiences of Elementary student leaders: president, vice president and secretary. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences that elementary student leaders undergo while fulfilling their leadership roles?
2. How do the student leaders cope with the challenges they encounter while fulfilling their leadership responsibilities?
3. What insight can elementary student leaders offers to their fellow students and to the broader academic community about the obstacles they face in the school?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative type of research in phenomenological approach in order to comprehend the participants' points of view. The target audience for this methodology was qualitative researchers. It used in-depth, focused study on a small sample of people to help and support the development of hypotheses. Information obtained through observation, conversation, depiction, and interviews. The collected data was accurately assessed and analyzed. The majority of qualitative research uses naturalistic, interpretive, and inductive methods. Additionally, the strategies help the researcher build rapport with the participants. This makes it simpler for the researcher to communicate with the participants, which enhances the validity and dependability of the data (Mayan, 2016).

In context, the research design for this study was qualitative in nature. It was for the purpose of exploring and understanding the experiences of the elementary student leaders. I was able to acquire the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of the main participants by employing this design, which would not be feasible if I utilize quantitative research methodologies.

Meanwhile, I employed phenomenology, which focuses on understanding and highlighting specific phenomena from the perspectives of those directly involved. This approach, viewed from a human-centric lens, typically involves gathering detailed insights and perceptions using inductive, qualitative methods like discussions, participant observation, and interviews, presenting the findings from the participants' viewpoints (Lune & Berg, 2017).

Phenomenology was used since it was really useful for our academic project. I became aware of the necessity of performing phenomenological research in the local setting when I recognized my study focused solely on exploring the lived experiences of the participants, who were elementary school pupils. This research approach allowed me to gain deeper insights into the lifestyles of both the participants and the informants.

Participants

The key participants of my study were the elementary student leaders. Upon participant selection, I employed purposive sampling to ensure that the only those who could give necessary data would be able to participate in my study. In recruitment process, there are criteria that need to be followed: (a.) each participant must be elementary student leaders in Asuncion District; (b.) the participant must also elementary student leaders: president, vice president and secretary; and above these, (c.) the participant must be Grade 5&6.

In this study I had fourteen participants, seven for in-depth interview and seven for focus group discussion. The fourteen participants were chosen accordingly with specific preferences. Seven (7) was undergo in-depth interviews (IDI) individually by me. Whereas, the other seven participants was in focus group discussion (FGD) which they gathered in the same place and time discussing the questions I was presented. As Creswell (2013) suggested that the number of participants which is ideal in qualitative study, specifically in phenomenological, ranges from 3 to 15 participants. Through having this set of participants, the collection of data will be sufficient enough for this kind of study.

Procedure

As a researcher, I underwent a number of procedures to compile data and other crucial details for the investigation. Before I began the study, I sought advice from my advisor to choose the best course of action. Before the studies had began, I had made this preparation.

To make the analysis and interpretation of the data easier to do, I made sure the data gathering methods were done properly. I made sure to get in touch with the people I wanted to interview and got an idea of when they were available. I first asked permission to speak with the ten elementary school students who were chosen for this study. I personally told the subjects, who were overweight primary school pupils, about the study. I felt it was crucial to make the participants aware of the study's objectives and purpose.

Before the actual interviews, the participants had the opportunity to be informed about the purpose of the study. In this qualitative research, interviews were the primary methods employed for data collection. These qualitative data gathering approaches aim to provide valuable insights into the underlying processes and changes in individuals' perspectives. In order to present the participants and request their agreement to participate in the study, it was important to me as the researcher to have a clear grasp of the nature and goal of the research (Smith, 2013).

The interview results were shared, transcribed, and analyzed. The data was examined and interpreted in relation to the study's issues. To strengthen the findings, the results were backed by relevant studies and literature, ensuring both validity and reliability of the emerging themes and other necessary data would be questioned.

Data Analysis

The gather data in my research was presented and examined in my study depending on the research's objectives or goals. In order to draw the study's results, a detailed analysis of the content of the participants' responses is required. In order to find answers to the research questions asked in this study, common patterns were sought after during data analysis.

Qualitative content analysis was the collection of samples usually consisting of purposely selected instances that reflect the investigated research questions. The idea was necessary to keep balanced subjectively and objectively. It pays attention to unique themes that illustrate the meanings of the phenomenon rather than numeric significance (Shannon, 2005).

The collected and obtained data were examined in this study using theme analysis. The goal of the data collection phase was to look for any patterns that suggest the concepts the participants represent. The information was then put into categories that made sense and summarized the letter's manuscript. Thematic analysis, a versatile qualitative analytical method, enables the researcher to derive fresh insights and ideas from the data.

Additionally, thematic analysis was a helpful approach of investigation when attempting to learn about people's ideas, opinions, knowledge, experiences, or beliefs from a collection of qualitative data, such as interview transcripts, social media profiles, or survey findings. Depending on the goals of the research and the analytical process, the application of themes once they have been identified can be variable. Theme analysis is a popular tool used by academics to better comprehend the content and get closer to their data (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Moreover, I completed the procedures for becoming familiar with the data, developing rough codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and identifying themes, and producing the report. The beginning of the analytical process was transcription. Divide it into pieces or components by analyzing it. The researcher went through a process where they attempted to evaluate the data they had acquired.

Lastly, I ultimately listen to the participants' recorded interviews to make the coding process simpler later on, and I took notes as I did so. I reviewed the data multiple times to become comfortable with the responses and quickly identify the most common ones. I developed a couple themes using these common responses, which I then condensed into a handful. I removed irrelevant data using data reduction techniques and turned it into useful study material for readers. I organized and sorted a substantial amount of qualitative data, effectively integrating and categorizing it. Data display techniques were used to exhibit the data in matrices, charts, and graphs so that readers could make their own conclusions.

Ethical Considerations

A set of ethical standards that functioned as a guide for study designs and processes must always be followed by scientists and researchers when collecting data from humans. Human research typically aims to comprehend real-world events, investigate powerful remedies, examine behavior, and improve lives in various ways. When conducting research, ethical standards must be followed. These factors function to uphold the academic or scientific integrity, increase the validity of the research, and protect the rights of research participants (Bhandari, 2022).

Respect for persons was an ethical principle that emphasizes consideration for other people and acknowledges their inherent autonomy. By giving participants enough information about the nature and purpose of this research study in the participant's information leaflet in a comprehensible way to improve their informed consent, the concept of autonomy can be upheld (Kalu & Bwalya, 2017).

In this study, an informed consent form was made in advance for the study's participants. People who were interested in the study were able to learn more about it thanks to the form's extensive information. Throughout the interviews, the researcher respected the thoughts and points of view of the participants. Building trusting relationships with the participants was crucial, as was considering their beliefs, customs, and way of life and giving them the choice to participate or not. Because the study was conducted after the relevance of the subjects, they were always respected. Prior to each interview, the participant gave the researcher permission to record the full

conversation, including their comments. Additionally, the participants were always informed of their rights to get information regarding the study's findings.

It was important that a person's decision to participate in the research was voluntary and based on accurate knowledge about the implications of their involvement. Consent was formalized in order to protect people's right to choose whether or not to engage in the research, and to foster research interactions that were built on "trust and integrity." In the past, ensuring the legitimacy of permission was a prerequisite (Klykken, 2021).

In order to respect ethical research standards, the study's participants were invited to make informed choices and actively participate. They were informed of their rights, which included the freedom to ask questions at any moment without being required to provide an explanation, the right to reject to answer questions that were sensitive. Any participant who wishes to quit the interview is respected by the researcher's decision. Every participant was eager and motivated to contribute to the success of the study because the researcher had made sure of this. The researcher got approval to record every interview in order to thoroughly understand the participants' experiences.

Beneficence emphasizes that the study should be beneficial to those who would participate in it rather than risky. It necessitates a dedication to reducing dangers to study participants rather than generating earnings owing to them. To avoid putting any participant at risk, the interviewee's identity will be kept anonymous. Participants were protected at all times, and no file of information was left unattended or unsecured (Kirsh, 2019).

In this context, the study is important to all of us, from student, teachers and the school administrator, because the purpose of this study was to showcase and address the various experiences of elementary student leaders: president, vice president and secretary, which would serve as the basis for the improvement of the leadership skills as well as a motivation by other students to pursue their leadership journey. This is a big benefits to Asuncion District as this can serve as a good reference to take actions of the experiences encountered by the elementary student leaders regarding the journey as well as to highlight best experiences of the elementary student leaders as a good example to be attained by the students.

In the research and findings, confidentiality is an issue, along with participant safety. The identities of the participants were kept secret. All materials, including videotapes, encrypted transcripts, notes, and other artifacts, should be destroyed after the data has been analyzed. Some of the informants were reluctant to participate in the interview at first because they didn't know what to say, but when I reassured them that their comments would remain private, they gave me the chance to appear at ease when responding to the interview questions. The questions are being asked with greater caution, and this research has been respected.

I used discrete coding to ensure that each participant could be located. In order to ensure participant anonymity, this clause was based on Republic Act 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which states that any information that could be used to identify participants by name, gender, ethnicity, or occupation should be expressed appropriately. Therefore, appropriate coding and other security measures were put in place to protect the participants' identities. Furthermore, none of the participants in my study were ever required to provide their names on any forms used for the study. The interviews were also verbatim transcribed by the researcher. Three years after the study's completion, research data must be archived and then destroyed.

Justice involved the equitable treatment of all individuals, ensuring equal opportunities and avoiding unfairness or bias at any stage of the research process, in participant selection, regardless of age, gender, race, religion, socioeconomic level, or any other criteria (Farrugia, 2019).

The researcher expressed sincere gratitude and recognition for the invaluable contributions made by all participants in the study. As a gesture of appreciation for their time and efforts in the interviews, the researcher thoughtfully offered souvenirs or tokens of appreciation. Furthermore, to ensure a fair and appropriate selection process, the researcher employed purposive sampling, meticulously selecting interview participants based on predefined inclusion criteria that were closely aligned with the study's objectives.

Results and Discussion

This section was divided into four parts: Part one talked about the participants data from which the qualitative data were collected; part two covered the data analysis procedures and the steps in the categorized of the emergent themes from the result of the in-depth interviews and focus group discussion; part three dealt with the responses to the interview and FGD question under were each research problem; part four contained the summary of the responses.

Participant

The participants of this study were the Elementary Student Leaders in Asuncion District; president, vice president and secretary. As depicted in Table 1, there were 14 people involved in this study; seven (7) for the focus group discussion and seven (7) for the in-depth interview.

In-depth Interview. There were seven key informants in this study who were all Elementary Student Leaders in Asuncion District; president, vice president and secretary. Following the principle of confidentiality, each informant for the in-depth interviews were

assigned a pseudonym during the conduct of interview, which assignment was made according to their unique physical characteristics and attitudes shown during the interview sessions. For instance, Ms. Active was the name given to the informant who has been active during the interview, while Ms. Journalist was the name given to the informant who has been a journalist. Mr. Heartthrob was the name given to the informant who has many girls who have a crush on him. Ms. Pretty was the name given to the informant who has morena beauty. Ms. Approachable was the name given to the informant who has an approachable personality. Mr. Athletic was the name given to the informant who has been a participant in sports especially taekwondo. Additionally, Mr. Friendly was the name given to the informant who has a personality of friendly during interview.

Focus Group Discussion. In the same manner, the seven participants of the focus group discussion were also given pseudonym. They were Ms. Serious, Ms. Helpful, Ms. Joyful, Ms. Shy, Mr. Tall, Mr. Adventurous and Ms. Patient. The participant was named Ms. Serious who has been the most serious during interview. Ms. Helpful was the name given to the participant who has been helpful to other students. Ms. Joyful was the name given of the participant who has been a happy go lucky during the interview. Ms. Shy was the name given of the participant who has been the shyest during the interview. While, Mr. Tall was the given name of the participant because of his height and Mr. Adventurous was the given name of the participant who has been love to travel. Additionally, Ms. Patient was the given name to the participants who has been very patient with other students.

The in-depth interview was conducted via face-to-face with the time that was accessible for each informant, and the focus group discussion was conducted also via face-to-face.

The researcher used smartphones to record the data given by the participants; for recording of data is a very important factor for the validity and credibility of the study.

Table 1. Participants of the Study

<i>In-Depth Interview (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Code</i>
1. Ms. Active	13	Female	IDI-01
2. Ms. Journalist	12	Female	IDI-02
3. Mr. Heartthrob	13	Male	IDI-03
4. Ms. Pretty	12	Female	IDI-04
5. Ms. Approachable	13	Female	IDI-05
6. Mr. Athletic	13	Male	IDI-06
7. Mr. Friendly	12	Male	IDI-07
Total=7			
<i>Focus Group Discussion (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Code</i>
1. Ms. Serious	13	Female	FGD-01
2. Ms. Helpful	12	Female	FGD-02
3. Ms. Joyful	13	Female	FGD-03
4. Ms. Shy	13	Female	FGD-04
5. Mr. Tall	13	Male	FGD-05
6. Mr. Adventurous	12	Male	FGD-06
7. Ms. Patient	12	Female	FGD-07
Total=7			

Categorization of Data

After the validated research questions were conducted in-depth interviews and focus group discussion, the audio-recording were transcribed, translated and analyzed. The analysis began with the coding process, Coding process of organizing the materials into chunks of segment of texts before bringing the meaning to information.

Coding process is used to generate a description of the setting of people as well as categorized of themes for analysis. These themes were used to shape into a general description of the phenomenon being studied. Data results were presented in form of table. The gathered data was handed the assigned data analyst to approved and verified the data and the emerging themes that the researchers has made and analyzed.

To categorize the data, the themes were presented by research questions and referred to as major themes. The themes which emerged from the study were thoroughly discussed to provide a vivid description. Adjacent to the major themes in the table were the core ideas from the responses of the participants.

In order to add trustworthiness of the study, the researcher made a note of the dimensions of credibility and transferability. To address credibility, member verification was carried out in addition to the triangulation approach. This was accomplished by providing copies of the interview transcript to participants so they may remark on it and certify to its authenticity.

Regarding transferability, the researcher said right away that the results were not generally applicable since these views were solely based on the participants personal experiences in the particular school.

Research Question No.1: What are the lived experiences that elementary student leaders undergo while fulfilling their leadership roles?

In order to answer this research questions, in-depth interviews and focus group discussion were conducted with the informants and participants. Several sub-questions were asked to elicit their concept in regards to their experiences as an Elementary Student Leaders; president, vice president and secretary.

The major themes and supporting statements for research question number 1 was presented in Table 2. Participants had their responses towards their own experiences. From the answers of the participants, four major themes emerged and these were the following: Considering the Essential Traits and Duties of Student-Leaders; Humility in Leadership; Difficulty in Balancing Leadership Responsibility and academics; and Embracing the Responsibilities Wholeheartedly.

Table 2. Lived Experiences of the Elementary Student Leaders undergo while fulfilling their leadership roles

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Considering the Essential Traits and Duties of Student-Leaders	<p>“Being enthusiastic, having some perseverance, enthusiasm and being an active student not only in academic but also in extracurricular activities. Moreover, I also support the welfare of our school.”-IDI-02</p> <p>“A good student leader shall have number of qualities they should have strong communication skills be organized and have strong problem-solving skills they should also be able to inspire and motivate others additionally they should be open to feedback and have a positive attitude.”-IDI-07</p> <p>“You must be knowledgeable enough of what you are going or running since this is not only a gem but a responsibility because there are a lot of student leaders running and aiming a reward and not considering the responsibility of that position they running for.”-IDI-03</p> <p>“The things that I need to prepare in my position as student leader is stay authentic, keep an open mind and always listen, know how to delegate tasks to achieve common goals learn from mistakes to improve for the future and seek knowledge.”-FGD-04</p> <p>“Serving as a good example, be a good model specially the low grade 1 to 4 and another is keeping your role or responsibility well does your promise during the campaign work hard to do it and lastly be friendly, responsible, kind and respectful.”-FGD-01</p>
Humility in Leadership	<p>“Being respectful is also being a kind because they said that grade 6 or the SELG officer they need to be a role model to other student that's why we do our best to be their role model.”-FGD-03</p> <p>“Experienced a willingness to acknowledge my limitations or mistakes and being humble even in your position they should not be boastful to other students.”-IDI-03</p> <p>“In my opinion, because you are a leader in your school, you should not feel that you are the top, you should not abuse others like it should be fair.”-IDI-04</p> <p>“I won't break the rules because I'm an officer, I won't claim myself that I'm so powerful to the point that it's like I'm a bully, I have to train them to listen to me.”-IDI-05</p>
Difficulty in Balancing Leadership Responsibilities and Academics	<p>“For me the positive effects as an elementary student leader is to sharpen my mind as a responsible individual, I experienced difficulty in handling situations and challenges in terms of problems that will come, I was able to practice balance and in managing my responsibilities and academics. Meanwhile, the negative things that affect me as a student leader is for example I want to go home but I can't because there are some responsibilities at school that have to be completed and every morning instead of going directly to my classroom, I still have to gather with the officer to get ready for the list of late comers then roving per classroom.”- IDI-02</p> <p>“You know how to manage well the responsibilities and the future problem that might come to you as a leader though it was hard to being to manage the responsibilities over academics, but we must persist”-IDI-07</p>
Embracing the Responsibilities Wholeheartedly	<p>“It is really difficult to managing being a leader and a student at the same time-FGD-02</p> <p>“I had trouble in managing my responsibilities well.” -FGD-01</p> <p>“The positive things that student brought to me personally are they encourage me personally my classmate or best friends to work hard and I was able to accept all my responsibilities heartily,”-FGD-03</p> <p>“Accept the responsibility and manage it properly. Also, to be open minded to the other students who are around me, we will teach them the right things to do.”-FGD-05</p> <p>“It was quite fun and self-fulfilling; we just have to accept wholeheartedly that we have responsibilities.”- IDI-01</p>

Considering the Essential Traits and Duties of Student-Leaders

Student leaders in elementary school endure a great deal of responsibility. Despite their age, these young leaders set a good example for their peers by living according to the school’s ideals. They selected not just on the basis of their academic performance but also on the basis of their positive behaviors, which include obligation, open communication, kindness and ability to solve problem. Their responsibilities go beyond the classroom.

Ms. Journalist (pseudonym) shared her experience as a driven and passionate student who excels in both extracurricular and academic pursuits. Her unwavering commitment to excellence is evident in her continuous efforts to enhance the welfare of her school community. Through her dedication and hard work, she not only achieves academic success but also actively contributes to the

betterment of her school environment. She stated that:

“Ang pagkamadasigon, naay some kadasig ug usa ka active nga students dili lang sa academic kung dilis sa mga extracurricular activities sa ug ako sang ginasuportahan ang kaayohan sa among eskwelahan”, (IDI-02)

(Being enthusiastic, having some perseverance, enthusiasm and being an active student not only in academic but also in extracurricular activities. Moreover, I also support the welfare of our school.)

Then Mr. Friendly (pseudonym) shared that a good student leader must have a strong resolving problems, teamwork and social abilities are just a few of the many traits of a successful student leader. By embodying these traits and leading by example, student leaders can make a lasting impact on their peers and contribute significantly to the growth and development of the school community as a whole. He stated that:

“Ang maayo nga student leader kay naay pipila ka mga qualities nga kinahanglan and they should have strong communication skills ug naay strong problem-solving skill kinahanglan usab sila makahimo sa pagdasig sa uban dugang pa kinahanglan sa sila open sa mga feedback ug naay positive nga kinaiya”, (IDI-07)

(A good student leader shall have number of qualities they should have strong communication skills be organized and have strong problem-solving skills they should also be able to inspire and motivate others additionally they should be open to feedback and have a positive attitude.)

Furthermore, Mr. Heartthrob (pseudonym) shared his experience that being student leaders most have an ability to handle their roles and responsibility since it is not a precious asset but an important obligation for student leader there are some student leaders is looking for reward rather than a responsibility of the position they running for. He stated that:

“Dapat kabalo naka kung unsa imong gi daganan or imong gihimo kay dili lng mani murag trophy pag maka daug na pero kani kay responsibility man kay naay uban student leaders nga ni dagan ug naga aim sa reward and wala nila gina considered and responsibility ana nga position sa ilang gi daganan”, (IDI-03)

(You must be knowledgeable enough of what you are going or running since this is not only a gem but a responsibility because there are a lot of student leaders running and aiming a reward and not considering the responsibility of that position they running for.)

Moreover, Ms. Shy (pseudonym) shared her challenging preparation for her role as a student leader, emphasizing the importance of sincerity, a willingness to learn, and effective delegation. She highlighted these qualities as essential for fostering teamwork and achieving common goals within the school community. By embodying these traits, student leaders can create a positive and productive environment that promotes collaboration and success among their peers. She said:

“Ang mga butang nga kanahanglan Nakong andamon sa akong posisyon isip student leader ang magpabiling matinud anon, magpabilin nga abli ang huna huna ug kanunay nga maminaw, kahibalo unsaon pag delegate sa mga buluhaton aron ma achieve ang common nga tumong gikan sa mga sayop arom molambo alang sa umaabot and para to seek knowledge”, (FGD-04)

(The things that I need to prepare in my position as student leader is stay authentic, keep an open mind and always listen, know how to delegate tasks to achieve common goals learn from mistakes to improve for the future and seek knowledge.)

Additionally, Ms. Serious (pseudonym) shared her essential qualities needed to be a role model for younger students, emphasizing the importance of giving her best effort, fulfilling her election promises, and carrying out her responsibilities and diligently. She exemplified virtues of responsibility, kindness, and respect, demonstrating a commitment to setting a positive example for her peers and inspiring those in the lower grades to follow suit. She stated that:

“Mahimo kang good example sa uban students ug mahimong role model samot na sa mga lower grade nya dapat buhaton gyud nimo ang mga responsibility ug tarong katong imong mga promise katong pag campaign pa dapat imo”, (FGD-01)

(Serving as a good example, be a good model specially the low grade 1 to 4 and another is keeping your role and or the responsibility well does your promise during the campaign work hard to do it and lastly be friendly, responsible, kind and respectful.)

Lastly, Ms. Joyful (pseudonym) shared her experience as a grade 6 student leader, striving to lead by example and inspire her peers to work diligently. Through her positive attitude and dedication, she aims to encourage her classmates to excel

and embody the qualities of a responsible and motivated student leaders. Through her leadership and enthusiasm, she aims to cultivate a culture of hard work, positivity, and mutual support within her school community. She said that:

“Ang pagiging respectful mao to siya ang pagiging buotan kay mag ingon man gud sila nga ang grade 6 or ang mga officer kay kailangan naa sa ila ang pagiging role model sa mga bata so mao to gina buhat namo among best para ang uban bata sad mo sundog sa amoa”, (FGD-03)

(Being respectful is also being a kind because they said that grade 6 or the SELG officer they need to be a role model to another student that's why we do our best to be their role model.)

Humility in Leadership

This was the second essential theme drawn from responses of the participants during in-depth interview and focus group discussion. It was revealed during that interview that being humble in leadership is an essential trait, especially for elementary student leaders. It includes understanding one's own limitations as well as the worth of other people. It promotes an attitude of trust, unity and development by encouraging a belief of shared obligation. Student leaders that are humble tend to be willing to listen to criticism and training, which allow them to grow and change.

Mr. Heartthrob (pseudonym) candidly revealed that his growth as a student leader was shaped by acknowledging and learning from his shortcomings and failures. Through self-awareness, he recognized that embracing setbacks and challenges was essential for his personal and leadership development. His journey taught him that resilience and a growth mindset are key factors in overcoming obstacles and evolving as a successful student leader. He said that:

“Experience a willingness nga ilhon lang gyud ang mga mali nga mga butang nya dapat kabalo sa limitations and ang pagiging humble lang sad bisan paman sa imong posisyon nga na abot dili lang gyud dapat ka mahinambugon sa uban students”, (IDI-03)

(Experienced a willingness to acknowledge my limitations or mistakes and being humble even in your position they should not be boastful to other students.)

In addition, Ms. Pretty (pseudonym) candidly shared her thought that a school leader it is essential to treat everyone equally, abstain from misusing power and promote an atmosphere of equality and respect rather than to think of themselves as superior. By promoting a culture of mutual respect and understanding, she aims to create a harmonious and supportive atmosphere where all individuals feel valued and empowered. She mentioned that:

“Sa akoo kay kintahay leader naka sa imohang school dapat dili ka feel nimo nga ikaw nay taas nya kailangan na nimo dili abusohon ang uban like fair ra dapat”, (IDI-04)

(In my opinion, because you are a leader in your school, you should not feel that you are the top, you should not abuse others like it should be fair.)

Similarly, Ms. Approachable (pseudonym) illustrate that as an officer she need to maintain to regulate the rules without using violence or harassing instead she will put her attention on building people's respect and promoting a mindset of respect for one another and active listening. By promoting a mindset of respect and empathy, she aimed to create a safe and inclusive environment where all members of the school community feel valued and heard. She mentioned that:

“Dili ko molabag sa mga rules kay officer ko dili ko mag claim sa akong self nga power na kaayo ko to the point nga murag mang bully nako dapat akoo silang itrain nga maminaw sa akoo”. (IDI-05)

(I won't break the rules because I'm an officer, I won't claim myself that I'm so powerful to the point that it's like I'm a bully, I have to train them to listen to me.)

Difficulty in Balancing Leadership Responsibilities and Academics

For elementary student leaders, seeking a balance between leadership duties and academics can be difficult. While it takes time and attention they are expected to perform academically effectively. However, they also have to take part in an array of activities, make significant decisions and mentor their peer because of their leadership positions. If this dual duty is not effectively handled it may result in stress, pressure and even a decline in academic achievement. To overcome these obstacles, it is essential that these young leaders acquire time management techniques and successfully prioritize their responsibility.

Ms. Journalist (pseudonym) candidly shared the difficulty in balancing her responsibility as a student leader and academics just like she said that there are certain disadvantages such as time when she wanted to go home but unable to because of unfinished obligation at school, to complete her duties every morning like making a list of being late and monitoring classroom rather than going to her classroom directly and she shared what are the benefits if it is successfully manage both leadership responsibility and her academics. She said:

“Para sa akoo ang positive na effect sa akoo as elementary student leader kay mas mahasa ang akoang pang hunahuna as a responsible individual, nakabalo ko kung unsaon pag handle ug mga situations and challenges in terms of nay mga problema nga muabot I became more responsible not only for myself but also for my duties. Meanwhile, the negative things that affects me as a student leader kay for example ting uli na inig ka hapon tapos gusto nako mouli pero dili pa pwede kay naa pakuy dapat humanon na responsibilities”. (IDI-02)

(For me the positive effects as an elementary student leader is to sharpen my mind as a responsible individual, I experienced difficulty in handling situations and challenges in terms of problems that will come, I was able to practice balance and in managing my responsibilities and academics. Meanwhile, the negative things that affect me as a student leader is for example I want to go home but I can't because there are some responsibilities at school that have to be completed and every morning instead of going directly to my classroom.)

Similarly, Mr. Friendly (pseudonym) shared that regardless of dealing with leadership duties with academic obligations might be difficult, it's important to strive and develop the skills necessary to deal with issues and responsibilities that may come up as leader in the coming decades. By prioritizing skill development and adaptability, Mr. Friendly aims to equip himself for the evolving demands and responsibilities of leadership in the future. He mentioned that:

“Dapat kabalo ka ug unsaon nimo pagdala ang mga responsibilidad ug ang umaabot nga problema nga mahimong moabot nimo isip usa ka leader bisan kung lisod and pag manage sa mga responsibility over academics pero kinahanglan gihapon namong magpadayun”, (IDI-07)

(You know how to manage well the responsibilities and the future problem that might come to you as a leader though it was hard to being to manage the responsibilities over academics, but we must persist.)

Additionally, Ms. Helpful (pseudonym) candidly expressed the challenges of balancing the demands of leadership and academics simultaneously. She acknowledged the complexity of managing both responsibilities effectively while striving to excel in both areas. Despite the difficulty, Ms. Helpful remains committed to navigating this balance and maximizing her potential in both leadership and academic pursuits. She said that:

“Lisod kaayo ang pagdumala isip usa ka leader ug student at the same time”, (FGD-02)

(It is really difficult to managing being a leader and a student at the same time.)

Furthermore, Ms. Serious (pseudonym) shared her experience how struggle finding the right balance and setting priorities for her various responsibilities, which posed challenges in effectively managing her duties. The struggle to juggle competing demands made it challenging for her to navigate her responsibilities successfully and meet expectations in both leadership and academic realms. She answered that:

“Na problema ko sa pagdumala sa akong mga responsibilities sa tarong nga pamaagi”, (FGD-01)

(I had trouble in managing my responsibilities well.)

Embracing the Responsibilities Wholeheartedly

As an elementary student leader, they wholeheartedly embraced their responsibility with passion and unwavering commitment. They not only took a leading role in school activities but also diligent preparation events, demonstrating exceptional organizational skills and a proactive approach to leadership. Despite the challenges of being an elementary student leader, they remained resilient and dedicated, setting a shining example for their peers through their perseverance and positivity. Their ability to navigate through difficulties with grace and determination inspired those around them, earning them respect and admiration from both students and teachers alike.

Ms. Joyful (pseudonym) shared her experiences on how she accepts all her responsibilities allowed her to recognize the positive impact of being a student leader, as she observed the supportive influence of her classmates and best friend. Their inspiration motivated her to work diligently and fulfill her obligations as an elementary student leader, fostering a sense of personal growth and determination. She mentioned that:

“Ang mga positive nga mga butang nga gidala isip student sa personal mao ang nagdasig sa akong mga classmates or kanang close gyud nako nga mga friends to work hard and madawat nako tanan Nakong mga responsibility nga kinasing kasing”, (FGD-03)

(The positive things that student brought to me personally are they encourage me personally my classmate or best friends to work hard and I was able to accept all my responsibilities heartily.)

Similarly, Mr. Tall (pseudonym) also shared that not only managed and accept all the responsibilities properly but also to prove to their fellow students that they were also open-minded and willing to help them find the right way to do things. He emphasized the importance of not only fulfilling duties but also guiding and assisting peers in navigating challenges and making informed decisions. He said that:

“Accept the responsibility and open mind gyud sa mga uban student nga naka palibot sa akong nya tudluan sila ug tarung nga mga buhatunon”. (FGD-05)

(Accept the responsibility and manage it properly. Also, to be open minded to the other students who are around me, we will teach them the right things to do.)

In addition, embracing responsibilities wholeheartedly brought enjoyment and providing a feeling of accomplishment, as seen in the case of Ms. Active (pseudonym) by emphasizing the significance of fully accepting and engaging with her duties, she found fulfillment and a sense of purpose in her role as a student leader. She mentioned that:

“Kani kay medyo makalingaw ug makatagbaw sa kaugalingon kinahanglan lang namong dawaton sa kinasingkasing nga naa gyud me mga responsibility”, (IDI-01)

(It was quite fun and self-fulfilling; we just have to accept wholeheartedly that we have responsibilities.)

Research Question No.2: How do the student leaders coped with the challenges they encounter while fulfilling their leadership responsibilities?

This question focused on understanding the strategies, techniques and the coping mechanisms made by the elementary student leaders to conquer the different challenges that they encountered while fulfilling their leadership responsibilities. It explored how these students navigate some obstacles in leadership in order for them to encourage and positively faced different activities despite of many challenges that they have. This question aimed to uncover the various techniques that the learners utilized to overcome different challenges they faced. The following theme were: Establishing Collaboration with others, Creating a Support System and lastly Keeping Oneself Motivated.

Table 3. *How the Elementary Student Leaders Coped with the Challenges they have encounter while fulfilling their leadership responsibilities*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Establishing Collaboration with others	<p>“I collaborate with them by asking what the best ways are to do things.”-IDI-03</p> <p>“I will ask for help from my classmates and my SPG adviser so that I can get an idea of what to do if I have problems.”-IDI-06</p> <p>“We work together to solve our problem.”-FGD-02</p> <p>“We work together to finish many things easily and also to finish other things, ask for help from co officers.”-FGD-04</p>
Creating a Support System	<p>“I trust myself and never be afraid to collaborate with someone if I can't do it anymore.”-FGD-07</p> <p>“Every time I encounter challenges I usually talk with my peers, mentor or to my family and asked them if what would be their advice or opinion about my situation if I have a problem. By that, I can get ideas on how to cope with my problem.”-IDI-02</p> <p>“I overcame the challenges because of the support of my co officers and my family. Usually, they always comfort me and cheer me up every time I encounter a problem.”-FGD-04</p> <p>“The passion I have to become a student leader and my family, peers and schoolmates who believe in me and support me.”-IDI-03</p> <p>“I always consulted and ask help my mentor to overcome the challenges.”-IDI-07</p>
Keeping Oneself Motivated	<p>“I overcame the challenges because of the support like the support of our workers.”-IDI-06</p> <p>“Willing to serve with my fellow students what motivates me is my co peers, friends and family. I also keep myself motivated for me to function well”-IDI-01</p> <p>“Keeping myself motivated and handling conflict appropriately.” FGD-04</p> <p>“I'm just say to myself that I can do this that you can reach the final if you don't have the background of being an officer, you will be down. You must have a project that can be done. I just wish that YES-O was there so that it wouldn't be too much of a struggle, we are already telling this to the adviser about that problem.”-FGD-07</p>

Establishing Collaboration with others

Prioritizing genuine interaction, willingness to listen and respect for others is crucial for developing strong connections with other elementary student leaders. Student leaders may effectively collaborate and accomplish each other goals by appreciating various perspectives of one another and implementing each team member's skills.

Mr. Heartthrob (pseudonym) reflect his strategies on collaborating to seek advice and recommendation as an elementary student leader, engage interacting with individuals by asking for suggestions and guidance on the most effective ways to get through things. He actively engaged with individuals by soliciting suggestions and guidance to navigate challenges effectively and make informed decisions. He said that:

“Nakipag collaborate ko sa ilaha pinaagi sa pagpangutana kung unsa ang mga pinakamaayong buhaton sa mga butang”, (IDI-03)

(I collaborate with them by asking what the best ways are to do things.)

In addition, Mr. Athletic (pseudonym) revealed his approach to overcoming obstacles by seeking guidance from his SPG adviser and peers. He shared his strategy of proactively seeking advice and support from trusted sources to navigate challenges effectively. By engaging with his SPG adviser and fellow students for advice, he demonstrated a proactive and collaborative mindset in addressing potential problems and finding solutions. He stated that:

“Mangayo kug tabang sa akong mga classmate and akong adviser sa SPG by that maka kuha kug idea kung unsa akong buhaton if naa kuy mga problema”. (IDI-06)

(I will ask for help from my classmates and my SPG adviser so that I can get an idea of what to do if I have problems.)

Moreover, Ms. Helpful (pseudonym) stated that by combining all strength, strategies and all they have they been able to solve their problem as a team through the use of each other's capabilities. They solve the problem together, demonstrating that working together is essential to overcome obstacles and utilizing individual strengths to achieve common goals and navigate difficulties successfully.

She said that:

“Magtinabangay dapat me para mas matadili ma solve among mga problema”. (FGD-02)

(We work together to easily solve our problem.)

Furthermore, Ms. Shy (pseudonym) supported that by working collaborate can do various tasks quickly and in circumstances of more challenging problems they seek assistance from their officers demonstrating a sense of cooperation and teamwork. By fostering a culture of teamwork and mutual support, she emphasized the value of collective effort in addressing difficult situations and achieving shared objectives. She mentioned that:

“Magtinabangay para dali ra mahuman nya daghan pakag mabuhat mangayog tabang sa co officers”. (FGD-04)

(We work together to finish many things easily and also to finish other things, ask for help from co officers.)

Lastly, Ms. Patient (pseudonym) shared her confidence in her abilities, acknowledging that when faced with tasks beyond her capacity, she is proactive in seeking assistance. This exemplifies her self-assurance and awareness of when to reach out for help, showcasing a mature and responsible approach to problem-solving. She said that:

“Gisaligan nako ang akong kaugalingon ug dili ko mahadlok nga makipag collaborate sa laing tao kung dili na gyud nako makaya”, (FGD-07)

(I trust myself and never be afraid to collaborate with someone if I can't do it anymore.)

Creating a Support System

The second essential theme drawn from responses of the participants during in-depth interview and focus group discussion. It was revealed that elementary student leaders sought for guidance and support along their leadership journey. This means that many participants actively sought motivation or help to these young leaders navigate challenges. This action showed a recognition that seeking appreciation and feedback that was helpful can also help them feel more motivated and confident. This setup helps student leaders become stronger leaders while also advancing their personal growth and establishing them for leadership position in the future.

Ms. Journalist (pseudonym) stated that when she faced difficulties, she frequently looked her family, mentor and peers for support. By getting their thoughts and recommendations, she may acquire understanding of the situation and come up with creative solution, she can access a variety of viewpoint and techniques with this way which help her deal with challenging circumstances more skillfully. She said that:

“Every time maka encounter ko ug mga challenges kay kasagaran makipag istorya ko sa akong peers, mentor or sa akong family and mangutana kung unsa ilang matambag o opinion bahin sa akong sitwasyon if naay kuy problem. Pinaagi ana makakuha ko ug unsaon pag cope sa akong problema”, (IDI-02)

(Every time I encounter challenges I usually talk with my peers, mentor or to my family and asked them if what would be their advice or opinion about my situation if I have a problem. By that, I can get ideas on how to cope with my problem.)

Similarly, Ms. Shy (pseudonym) candidly shared that her family and fellow officers' constant encouragement was essential in guiding her to succeed in overcoming obstacles since they never failed to sympathize and motivate her when she needed it through that she was given the strength to endure and solve her problems by their positive comments and their presence. She mentioned that:

“Nalampasan nako ang mga challenges tungod sa mga supporta sa akong co officers ug akong family. Kasagaran ila kung gina comfort and cheer me up every time nga naa kuy problema”, (FGD-04)

(I overcame the challenges because of the support of my co officers and my family. Usually, they always comfort me and cheer me up every time I encounter a problem.)

In addition, Mr. Heartthrob (pseudonym) highlighted that his goal to become a student leader serves as a driving force, propelling him forward in his journey. He expressed gratitude towards his family, friends, and fellow students who have consistently believed in him and offered unwavering support throughout his path to leadership. Their belief in him has been a source of motivation and encouragement, reinforcing his commitment to his goal of becoming a student leader. He mentioned that:

“Ang akong hilig nga mahimong leader sa mga students ug akong pamilya, peers and schoolmates nako nga nisalig sa akoa ug naga supporta”, (IDI-03)

(The passion I have to become a student leader and my family, peers and schoolmates who believe in me and support me.)

Likewise, Mr. Friendly (pseudonym) shared that he has consistently sought guidance and encouragement from his mentor to aid in his personal growth journey, enabling him to effectively navigate and conquer obstacles. The mentor's advice and support played a pivotal role in his achievements, providing the necessary guidance and motivation for his success. He said that:

“Permente ko naka consult ug ask help sa akong mentor para ma overcome nako ang mga challenges”, (IDI-07)

(I always consulted and ask help my mentor to overcome the challenges.)

Lastly, Mr. Athletic (pseudonym) stated that the passionate assistance of their dedicated mentors was important in which allow him to successfully overcome. The unwavering dedication and cooperation of his mentors provided him with the determination and inspiration needed to persevere and achieve his goals. Their guidance and encouragement fueled his motivation, instilling in him the resilience and drive to keep pushing forward and ultimately succeed. He mentioned that:

“Na overcome nako ang mga challenges kay tungod sa mga supporta like mga supporta sa mga workers namo mao lang”. (IDI-06)

(I overcame the challenges because of the support like the support of our workers.)

Keeping Oneself Motivated

This was the last essential theme drawn from responses of the participants during in-depth interview and focus group discussion. It was revealed in the interview that as an elementary student leaders there are several ways to stay motivated. Reflecting on oneself and appreciating modest but meaningful accomplishments are two other ways to stay inspired. As an elementary student leaders mentioned that one may further boost their inspiration and motivation by consistently recognizing the effort and commitment of both oneself and others.

Ms. Active (pseudonym) affirmed that her fellow classmates, colleagues and family provides her with support and companionship which motivates her to serve with them she inspired to stay guided and give her best work through the trust they have in her and the need to have a great impact on their lives. Through their unwavering support and belief in her abilities, she fueled to stay guided and dedicated to giving her best effort in all she does. She mentioned that:

“Willing to serve with my fellow student ang naga motivate sa akoa akong mga co peers, friends and family”. (IDI-01)

(Willing to serve with my fellow students what motivates me is my co peers, friends and family. I also keep myself motivated for me to function well.)

Additionally, Ms. Shy (pseudonym) shared that keeping motivation for oneself and effectively managing problems are essential abilities that help her overcome obstacles, establish harmonious connection and grow personally. Through perseverance and self-motivation, she cultivates resilience and interpersonal skills that enable her to tackle obstacles with confidence and maturity. She said that:

“Pagpanatiling motivated sa akong sarili ug handling conflict appropriately”, (FGD-04)

(Keeping myself motivated and handling conflict appropriately.)

Furthermore, Ms. Patient (pseudonym) illustrate that if student leader that lack of prior officer experience they easily down but despite the obstacle and she remind herself about the skills, optimize on creating a project that is attainable and voice her worries to the advisor in the hopes of receiving assistance from groups like YES-O to lessen any responsibilities she might face. She mentioned that:

“Ako rang gina ingon sa akong sarili nga laban lang maabot ra gyud ka sa final hapit na if wala kay background sa pagka officer ma down gyud ka nya dapat naa gyud kay project mabuhat gusto lang unta ko nga naa ang YES-O para dili kaayo struggle amoa nang gina ingnan among adviser about ana nga problem”. (FGD-07)

(I'm just say to myself that I can do this that you can reach the final if you don't have the background of being an officer, you will be down. You must have a project that can be done. I just wish that YES-O was there so that it wouldn't be too much of a struggle, we are already telling this to the adviser about that problem.)

Research Question No.3: What insight can elementary student leaders offers to their fellow students and to the broader academic community about the obstacles they face in the school?

In order to answer this research question, in-depth interviews and focus group discussion were conducted with the informants and participants. Several sub-questions were asked to elicit their concept in regards to their insight as Elementary Student Leaders.

The major themes and supporting statements for research question number 3 was presented in Table 4. Participants had their responses towards their insights. From the answer of the participants, three major themes emerged and these were the following: Must Possess Various Leadership Abilities, Leadership Empowers Communication and Confidence and lastly Effective Time Management and Prioritization in Leadership.

Must Possess Various Leadership Abilities

This was one of the emerging themes from response of the participants during in-depth interview and focus group discussion. It was revealed during interviews that to effectively carry out their responsibilities elementary student leaders need to have a wide range of leadership skills. Strong abilities to communicate to engage with peers and effectively convey ideas, decision-making abilities to make well informed determination, empathy and understanding to relate to others' needs, organizational abilities to manage tasks and

responsibilities and the capacity to encourage and inspire other students are a few of these. Elementary student leaders can make significant influence on their school community, promote teamwork and establish a pleasant and inclusive atmosphere by developing these leadership skills.

Table 4. *Insight of Elementary Student Leaders Offers to their fellow students and to the broader academic community about the obstacles they face in the school*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Must Possess Various Leadership Abilities	<p>“My advice is that they should have more confidence, be patient, be good to others and have good communication.”-IDI-01</p> <p>“If I were given a chance to advise them, I would say that they should be patient, they should know their responsibility to the school and the students, they should know how to handle and overcome problems and they also need to give way to their opinion, also with others so that they have unity and teamwork then they should know how to handle their time management between academic and leadership.”-IDI-02</p> <p>“I can advise them that sometimes you are tired, they should keep going as SPG, they should be active, they should be good at time management because some people don't run because they are afraid, but I talk to them since I can't run the next SPG election, they should not be afraid. because being SPG president can also help them.”-IDI-04</p> <p>“They must have a lot of patience because it is difficult to manage other students.”-IDI-07</p> <p>“Having commitment and being flexible being responsible, understanding and having honesty and communication.”-IDI-03</p>
Leadership Empowers Communication and Confidence	<p>“You should really humble, responsible respect for others and also determination.”-FGD-06</p> <p>“Being able to become a good communicator to others and in some reason, I can be and I can do that in every person I meet.”-IDI-01</p> <p>“It helps me boost my confidence and willingness to become a responsible individual not only for myself but also to where am I belong it molds me to become more competent and ready for the future and it helps me to overcome on how to become a proactive and resilient one.”-IDI-02</p> <p>“Believe in themselves or trust what they want to do in school It should be their want not just because you want it and for the char or popularity you should have a dedication and passion for being a student leader despite what position you're running for.”-IDI-03</p> <p>“It helps me to boost my ability to be a good communicator by being friendly and socializing with other students.”-FGD-03</p> <p>“In that way being a leader has really helped me, I have the confidence that it's okay for me to be an emcee even in the whole barangay.”-FGD-04</p>
Effective Time Management and Prioritization in Leadership	<p>“Be patient and must know how to juggle work and won't get angry when their work goes to yours.”-IDI-05</p> <p>“They should do their responsibilities and being a resilient person and they should know how to balance their time and teamwork so that they can be successful in being an officer.”-IDI-06</p> <p>“They must learn what to prioritize and when to prioritize things.”-FGD-01</p> <p>“Always prepare a plan and learn how to prioritize things for them didn't feel that they are pressure in terms of handling their positions and responsibility.”-FGD-05</p>

Ms. Active (pseudonym) suggest that student leaders strengthen strong interpersonal skills, cultivate empathy, compassion for others, and nurture self-confidence. This holistic approach to leadership development emphasizes the importance of emotional intelligence, understanding, and self-assurance in effectively guiding and supporting peers. These characteristics can significantly promote productive relationship as well as individual improvement. She said that:

“Akong advise is kinahanglan sila naa silay more confidence, be patient, be good to others and have good communication”. (IDI-01)
(My advice is that they should have more confidence, be patient, be good to others and have good communication.)

Similarly, Ms. Journalist (pseudonym) also suggest that in order to build unity and teamwork, she would recommend to put patience first, understand their obligations to the school and their peers, deal with difficulties in an efficient manner and encourage open-minded communication and cooperation also time management skills are essential for elementary student leaders to succeed in juggling leadership obligations and academic endeavors. She said that:

“If I were given a chance to advise them I would say nga dapat taas silay pasensya kabalo sila dapat sa ilang responsibilidad sa eskwelahan ug sa mga estudyante kabalo sila mo handle ug mo overcome ug mga problema ug kailangan pud nila mo giveway sa opinion pud sa uban aron naa silay unity and teamwork tapos dapat kabalo sila mo handle sa ilahang time management between academic and leadership”. (IDI-02)

(If I were given a chance to advise them, I would say that they should be patient, they should know their responsibility to the school and the students, they should know how to handle and overcome problems and they also need to give way to their opinion, also with others so that they have unity and teamwork then they should know how to handle their time management between academic and leadership.)

In addition, Mr. Adventurous (pseudonym) stated that gaining personal development and achievement requires embracing humility,

responsibility, respect for others and dedication. By embodying these values, individuals can navigate challenges, build meaningful relationships, and strive towards their goals with integrity and purpose and individuals can cultivate a strong foundation for personal development and achievement. He said that:

“Kinahanglan gyud nga mapaubsanon, responsible nga pagtahod sa uban nga determination”, (FGD-06)

(You should really humble, responsible respect for others and also determination.)

Furthermore, Ms. Pretty (pseudonym) stated that elementary student leaders embrace efficient time management to keep going even when they feel exhausted and to keep participating and active as SPG officers, she urge them to calmly get overcome any worries or uncertainties because becoming the president of SPG can lead to great memories and personal development. She mentioned that:

“Akong ma advise sa ilaha sometimes kapoy na kayo sila mo padayon gyud dapat sila sa ilang pagka SPG nya dapat active gyud sila dapat hawd sad sila sa time management kay ang uban dili mo dagan kay mahadlok pero ako silang gina istoryahan kay since dili naman ko pwede mo dagan sunod dapat dili mahadlok kay ang pagka SPG president kay maka tabang man sad sa ilaha”. (IDI-04)

(I can advise them that sometimes you are tired, they should keep going as SPG, they should be active, they should be good at time management because some people don't run because they are afraid, but I talk to them since I can't run the next SPG election, they should not be afraid. because being SPG president can also help them.)

Moreover, Mr. Friendly (pseudonym) said that being extremely patient is a considered important trait because it enables people to handle difficult circumstances with control and respect. It is a quality that makes it possible to endure difficulties while keeping one's control. People who possess patience are able to deal with hardship, recover aside from difficulties, and face challenges vigorously. He mentioned that:

“Kinahanglan nga sila naay taas nga pasensya kay lisod eh manage ang uban students”, (IDI-07)

(They must have a lot of patience because it is difficult to manage other students.)

Lastly, Ms. Joyful (pseudonym) also said that the future student leaders should promotes dedication and adaptability, exhibiting accountability and comprehension in all their pursuits. Their sincerity and strong communication abilities, which promote open communication and trust in their community, further strengthen their leadership. She mentioned that:

“Pagkakaroon nang commitment ug pagka flexible sa mga responsibility, pagsabot ug magkamatitud-anon ug communication”, (IDI-03)

(Having commitment and being flexible being responsible, understanding and having honesty and communication.)

Leadership Empowers Communication and Confidence

This was the second essential theme drawn from responses of the participants during in-depth interview and focus group discussion. It was revealed that in elementary student leaders, confidence and communication can be enhanced when leadership is appropriately cultivated. Installing leadership qualities in students is essential because it fosters confidence, self-reliance and effective communication. It has been demonstrated by researcher that when given the chance to lead and clear instruction, even young children can pick up leadership skills. Communication abilities, dependability, inventiveness, adaptability, accountability and an optimistic outlook are some of these attributes.

According to the experiences that shared by Ms. Active (pseudonym) being a student leader has helped her develop her communication skills, which she thinks essential for leadership. She makes an effort to speak clearly with everyone she come into deal with therefore what she could do isn't specific to any one person. By maintaining open and transparent communication with everyone she engages with, she ensures that her actions and decisions are inclusive and beneficial to all involved. She stated that:

“Being able to become a good communicator to others and in some reason, mahimo nako ug mahimo kana sa mga tao nga akong ma meet”, (IDI-01)

(Being able to become a good communicator to others and in some reason, I can be and I can do that in every person I meet.)

Additionally, Ms. Journalist (pseudonym) said that her confidence has grown and a feeling of accountability for herself and the community she is part of has been cultivated as a result of her experiences as a student leader. She is now a more capable person who is ready for the future through to these experiences, which have also taught her how to be proactive and resilient. She stated that:

“Nakatabang ni para ma boost akong confidence ug willingness para mahimong usa ka responsible nga individual dili lang para sa akong kaugalingon pero para sad sa asa ko na belong it molds me to become more competent ug ready para sa future ug nakatabang ni para ma overcome on how to become a proactive and resilient one”, (IDI-02)

(It helps me boost my confidence and willingness to become a responsible individual not only for myself but also to where am I belong it molds me to become more competent and ready for the future and it helps me to overcome on how to become a proactive and resilient

one.)

On the other hand, Mr. Heartthrob (pseudonym) also stated that pursuing student leadership should be done with true passion and dedication, not only for fame or money. No matter what role you're seeking, it's critical to have confidence in your abilities and your aspirations for the school, making sure that your activities are motivated by your desire to have a positive influence. He said that:

"I believe lang ilang mga sarili or I trust ang gusto nila buhaton sa school It should be imong want not just because gusto lang nimo and for the char or popularity you should have a dedication and passion for being a student leader despite what position you're running for". (IDI-03)

(Believe in themselves or trust what they want to do in school It should be their want not just because you want it and for the char or popularity you should have a dedication and passion for being a student leader despite what position you're running for.)

Furthermore, Ms. Joyful (pseudonym) explained that as a student leader she improved her communication skills by interacting with other students and creating a welcoming and social atmosphere. This has made it possible for her to build strong relationships and a feeling of solidarity among the students. By prioritizing open communication and inclusivity, she successfully built connections and fostered a supportive community within the student environment. She said that:

"It helps me para ma boost akong pagka good communicator pagka friendly and pagka socialize sa uban student". (FGD-03)

(It helps me to boost my ability to be a good communicator by being friendly and socializing with other students.)

Lastly, Ms. Shy (pseudonym) stated that her confidence has increased strongly as a result of being leader to the point that she feels at ease hosting events both inside and outside of the school including barangay events. My growth in confidence is a result of the knowledge and abilities she has gained as a student leader. She mentioned that:

"Happy sad ko nga gina himo ko nilag emcee kay fear gyud kaayo nako sauna ang mo atubang sa uban tao in that way naka tabang gyud ang pagka leader naa nakuy confidence okey na sa akua bisan pag sa buong barangay na mag emcee". (FGD-04)

(In that way being a leader has really helped me, I have the confidence that it's okay for me to be an emcee even in the whole barangay.)

Effective Time Management and Prioritization in Leadership

This was the third essential theme drawn from the responses of the participants during in-depth interview and focus group discussion. It was revealed during the interviews that for elementary student leaders efficient time management and prioritization are essential competencies. Student leaders can effectively complete their obligations by effectively managing their time to balance their commitments and obligations. By setting priorities, they can concentrate on the most crucial and significant facets of their leadership responsibilities to ensure enhancing their efficiency and influence.

Consequently, Ms. Approachable (pseudonym) affirmed that good student leader will be patient and have the capacity to handle their burden with kindness, which help them not become frustrated when they are given assignments from other people. By approaching tasks with patience and compassion, student leaders can navigate challenges with grace and lead by example in their interactions with peers. She stated that:

"Taas gihapon ug patient nya kabalo mo juggle ug work dili masuko pag ang trabaho niya maadto sa imoha". (IDI-05)

(Be patient and must know how to juggle work and won't get angry when their work goes to yours.)

In addition, Mr. Athletic (pseudonym) said that student leaders who are accomplished as officers must carry out their duties, responsibilities, develop resiliency and manage their time and teamwork well. Student leaders can succeed in their roles and have a positive influence on the school community by developing the skills of time management and teamwork. He mentioned that:

"Dapat buhaton nila ang ilang responsibilities and being a resilient person ug dapat kabalo sila mo balance sa ilang time nya teamwork aron ma success sila sa ilang pagka officer". (IDI-06)

(They should do their responsibilities and being a resilient person and they should know how to balance their time and teamwork so that they can be successful in being an officer.)

Moreover, Ms. Serious (pseudonym) stated that the capacity to identify and prioritize activities effectively as well as when to deploy time and resources to ensure best outcomes are critical features of effective leadership. Through strengthen these skills, individuals can navigate challenges, simplify processes, and lead their teams towards success with clarity and purpose. She stated that:

"Dapat maka tuon sila ug unsa ang unang buhaton and when to prioritize things". (FGD-01)

(They must learn what to prioritize and when to prioritize things.)

Lastly, Mr. Tall (pseudonym) also stated that being able to prioritize tasks effectively and continuously create and carry out organized strategies are an essential part of effective leadership. By mastering the art of task prioritization and strategic planning, he demonstrated

a commitment to efficient leadership practices and goal attainment. He mentioned that:

“Mag andam gyud daan ug mga plano ug unsay buhaton or unahon nga kabalo unsaon pag handle sa mga buhatunon para dili sila maka feel ug pressure in terms sa ilang pag handle sa ilang position ug responsibility”. (FGD-05)

(Always prepare a plan and learn how to prioritize things for them didn't feel that they are pressure in terms of handling their positions and responsibility.)

Conclusions

The results of this phenomenological study provided an opportunity to explore and comprehend the real-life experiences, challenges, coping strategies and valuable insights of elementary student leaders. With this gathered information, it was crucial to consider the implication it holds for enhancing the teaching experiences and meeting the specific needs of the elementary student leaders as they progress in their leadership journey.

The revelation that elementary student leaders experience challenges in considering the essential traits and duties of student-leaders. It suggested that these student leaders may encounter difficulty in balancing leadership responsibility and academics. The implication of this findings might offer assistance by promoting time managements abilities through seminars or a specific strategy a period of time. Workload can be distributed by promoting cooperation through shared initiatives and assignment. Establishing a solid support group involving educators, counselors or advisers, even fellow mentors enable leaders to obtain direction and exchange difficulties. Appreciating their leadership and reminding them of the importance they add to the school community can be a very effective motivator. Schools may enable future leaders to succeed in both academic and leadership roles by putting these principles into practices.

Moreover, elementary student leaders may use coping strategies shared by the participants including establishing collaboration with others, creating a support system and keeping oneself motivated can greatly benefits while fulfilling their leadership journey. These strategies may enable student leaders can monitor their development and acknowledge little victories to maintain motivated. Promoting teamwork utilizing collaborative endeavors and decision-making cultivates a feeling of common purpose and commitment then having a solid support system of peers, teachers and mentors enable leaders to exchange challenges, get advice and create a community that recognizes and celebrates their accomplishments.

Additionally, the findings that emphasized the importance of continuous support of this elementary student leaders and has significant implication for elementary school in Asuncion District. It means that these school need to prioritize and facilitate opportunities, trainings or workshops for all elementary student leaders especially the president, vice president and the secretary. By recognizing the value of supporting this elementary student leaders, schools in Asuncion District can ensure that their student leaders stay technics, strategies in dealing their peers, teacher, mentors and everyone around them and leadership methodologies. This commitment to continuous support of this elementary student leaders ongoing assistance is essential keeping up with mentors or teachers acknowledging their accomplishments and providing opportunity for them to discuss difficulties and celebrate victories are a few ways to do this. This continuous community of encouragement enables them to achieve success in their leadership endeavors. By embracing the importance of elementary student leaders in elementary school in Asuncion District may foster an environment of excellent and contribute to the institution.

Furthermore, providing leadership trainings, promoting communication and teamwork and strategic thinking skills can serve as an exemplary role model for their peers by exhibiting maturity and responsible behavior. Through the planning events that foster harmony and inclusivity, they contribute to the development of school-wide feeling of community. Apart from that, student leaders can improve their leadership abilities by studying effective communication and teamwork techniques by speaking up for their needs and opinions and working to create a more welcoming learning environment, they provide their fellow students a voice. These initiatives collectively contribute to the growth of elementary student leaders, ultimately improving the overall quality of this student leaders.

Lastly, for future researchers interested in studying the lived experiences of elementary student leaders, this study may provide valuable assistance in gathering necessary information for their own research. The finding, review of related literature and methodology employed in this study may serve as important references for their research papers.

Implications for Further Research

This study included the sample of fourteen (14) participants who were actively elementary student leaders: president, vice president and secretary specifically in grade 5 and grade 6 in Asuncion District. It is important to note that the selection oof participants was selected to the specific context, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to the other settings. This result can be shallow with limited statistically, which would weaken to overall research. When analyzing the result, it is crucial to take these limitations into consideration and to acknowledge the higher sample sizes will be required in future research to guarantee a deeper comprehension of the phenomenon.

Through the use of a phenomenological approach, the researcher was able to identify the fundamental themes and structures that define the event being investigated. The researcher suggested that as narrative research focuses on comprehending people's stories, experiences and perspectives through the lens of storytelling. By capturing the personal experiences of elementary student leaders. This

approach might enable as comprehensive examination of their distinct experiences. Difficulties and development as primary students. It may also provide an opportunity to uncover the contextual factors and emotions. The implication of narrative research allows for a deeper comprehension of the variety of issues faced by elementary student leaders offering insightful information that can motivate their fellow student leaders.

Lastly, a potential avenue for future research is to conduct a comprehensive analysis to explore the specific needs and challenges faced by the elementary student leaders: president, vice president and secretary while fulfilling their leadership journey. This in-depth investigation could identify critical areas as well as the benefits where the support and motivation are necessary to engage and enhance their personal growth as they explore with different elementary student leaders' activities and training. By gaining a deeper understanding of their experiences and addressing their individual needs, this research has the potential to better prepare and empower the learners, ultimately leading to improve the ways of elementary student leaders that help them encourage and motivate.

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